

Fractional concepts in neural networks: Enhancing activation functions

Vojtech Molek¹, Zahra Alijani^{1*}

Institute for Research and Applications of Fuzzy Modeling, University of Ostrava, Ostrava, 70103, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Zhaoxiang Zhang

Dataset link: https://gitlab.com/irafm-ai/frac_alc_ann

MSC:

41A05

41A10

65D05

65D17

Keywords:

Fractional calculus

Convolutional neural network

Activation function

Image classification

ABSTRACT

This study explores the integration of fractional calculus in neural networks by introducing fractional order derivatives (FOD) as tunable parameters in activation functions, enabling diverse function adaptation. We evaluate these fractional activation functions across datasets and architectures, comparing them with traditional and novel functions to assess their effects on accuracy, computational efficiency, and memory usage. Findings indicate that fractional functions, especially fractional Sigmoid, can yield better performance, though challenges persist.

1. Introduction

Fractional calculus pushes the boundaries of traditional derivatives and integrals by embracing orders that deviate from integer values [1]. The unique properties of fractional calculus have been shown to enhance the performance of artificial neural networks (ANNs) across various tasks [2,3].

In this paper, we revisit and expand upon the work of Zamora Esquivel et al. [4]; Zamora et al. [5]. The activation function is a fundamental component within a neural network, introducing nonlinearity essential for machine learning tasks, including classification and regression [6,7]. This paper emphasizes importance of selecting appropriate activation functions. Over the years, various neural network architectures have emerged, each with its distinctive activation functions ranging from sigmoid, RBF [8], ReLU [9], Softplus [10], Swish [11], Mish [12], and others. However, current practice predominantly relies on manual or automated [13] activation functions selection, often leading to an exhaustive trial-and-error and frequent retraining to find the optimal configuration.

Fractional calculus opens the door to entire families of functions by naturally extending the original function through fractional derivatives. Parameterization with a trainable argument places fractional activation functions in the same category as adaptive activation functions like

PReLU [14] or Swish. However, the application of fractional activation functions comes with its own set of challenges. One prominent challenge is the increased computational and memory complexity associated with fractional derivatives, which we discuss in Section 4. Moreover, research on fractional activation functions is limited, leaving the practical effectiveness of these functions still under-explored.

The fractional activation functions is a developing domain. In [15], the authors introduce Mittag-Leffler (M-L) functions, a class of parametric transcendental functions that generalize the exponential function. They present the derivative formula for M-L functions, showing its relation to the exponential function. In their experiments, manual fractional order adjustments led to improved accuracy using a simple multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with two hidden neurons. Fractional order values near 0 or 2 generally performed better. Increasing M-L calculation precision initially boosted accuracy, but performance plateaued beyond 260 terms.

In [4], a selection of fractional activation functions derived from Softplus, such as ReLU, hyperbolic tangent, and sigmoid was introduced. A combination of ResNet-18/20 and fractional activation functions outperformed ResNet-100/110 and standard activation functions. The networks were trained and tested on CIFAR-10 [16] and ImageNet-1K (IN-1K) [17]. However, the authors directly compare their fractional activation function results with those of He et al. [18]

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zahra.aliyani@osu.cz (Z. Alijani).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2025.02.013>

Received 19 August 2024; Received in revised form 4 December 2024; Accepted 10 February 2025

Available online 19 February 2025

0167-8655/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Fractional activation functions visualized. The functions in a row-major order are fractional Mish, fractional GELU, fractional sigmoid, and FALU [5]. Graph lines represent original functions (0.0 line) and their fractional derivations.

without providing an explanation of their training routine or a public repository.

The study in [5] presents the fractional adaptive linear unit (FALU), an activation function that generalizes earlier fractional models discussed in [4]. The authors manipulated and simplified formulas to derive final equations that eliminate computationally difficult terms such as the gamma function Γ . However, this simplification is not universally applicable to all fractional activation functions. Once again, the authors compared the results of established and custom ResNet architectures without explaining their training routine or providing a public repository.

The paper by Job et al. [19] introduced fractional ReLU and its variations using the expansion of the Maclaurin series. It highlights the flexibility of these functions compared to standard activation functions. Regression simulation studies were conducted to predict wind power generation, demonstrating the performance of ANNs (simple MLPs with one or two hidden layers) with fractional activation functions. In particular, fractional PReLU (FPReLU) and fractional LReLU (FLReLU) consistently outperformed their standard counterparts, with FLReLU exhibiting superior performance over LReLU.

To the best of our knowledge, the most recent effort in this area, published in 2024 [20], introduces activation functions derived using the improved Riemann–Liouville conformable fractional derivative (RL-CFD). In their experiments, the authors used MLPs with one or two hidden layers and trained on simple datasets such as the IRIS [21], MNIST [22], and FMNIST [23] datasets, in some cases achieving 100% test accuracy. However, in these experiments, the fractional order was a non-trainable parameter and had to be chosen manually, which significantly reduced the function’s potential.

In general, to the best of our knowledge, there is no publicly available implementation of any fractional activation functions. All the above-mentioned papers, except for [4,5], study fractional activation functions on limited datasets and simple shallow MLPs.

The main goals of our contribution are to evaluate published and new fractional activation functions using standard ANNs and datasets. The second goal is to provide a functional repository¹ with reproducible experiment settings.

2. Fractional calculus

Fractional calculus is an emerging area of research, with its application in neural networks still being experimental. Calculating the fractional derivative of certain activation functions is challenging, as

these may not have simple closed-form expressions. In such cases, approximations like the Grünwald–Letnikov method [1] or other specialized techniques are generally used. These methods involve approximating the fractional derivative using finite differences or numerical integration. Fractional derivatives and integrals are utilized in neural networks to modify the shape of activation functions during training. This modification is achieved by adjusting the FOD(s), which are trainable numerical parameter(s).

2.1. Fractional derivatives

Fractional calculus is a powerful mathematical tool for modeling various complex engineering and real-world systems. Three popular fundamental definitions of fractional derivatives are [24]:

The Grünwald–Letnikov [1] derivative of fractional order $a \in \mathcal{R}^+$ is defined as:

$$D^a f(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{h^a} \sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor \frac{x-a}{h} \rfloor} (-1)^n C_{n,a} f(x - nh), \quad (1)$$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ denotes the integer part of x and $C_{n,a}$ is the binomial coefficient. Grünwald–Letnikov fractional derivatives are often preferred in neural networks because they are easy to compute numerically and can be applied to various activation functions. This expression involves an infinite sum, making it challenging to represent directly as a convex combination. However, we can approximate it by considering a finite number of terms in the sum. Let us denote this finite approximation as $F_k(x)$, where k is the number of terms considered in the sum. Then, we have:

$$F_k(x) = \frac{1}{h^a} \sum_{n=0}^k (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(a+1)}{\Gamma(n+1)\Gamma(1-n+a)} \cdot f(x - nh). \quad (2)$$

$F_k(x)$ is considered as a convex combination of $f(x - nh)$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots, k$ with appropriate weights determined by the coefficients of the sum. Therefore, $F_k(x)$ can be expressed as:

$$F_k(x) = \sum_{n=0}^k w_n \cdot f(x - nh),$$

where w_n are the weights associated with each term in the sum.

The Riemann–Liouville derivative of fractional order $a \in \mathcal{R}^+$ is defined as:

$$D^a f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-a)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_a^x \frac{f(\mu)}{(x-\mu)^{a-n+1}} d\mu, \quad (3)$$

for $n-1 < a < n$, $n \in \mathcal{Z}^+$, and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function (we will recall it shortly). The Riemann–Liouville derivative is used when the initial conditions are given in terms of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals.

The Caputo derivative of fractional order $a \in \mathcal{R}^+$ is defined as:

$$D^a f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-a)} \int_a^x \frac{f^n(\mu)}{(x-\mu)^{a-n+1}} d\mu, \quad (4)$$

for $n-1 < a < n$, $n \in \mathcal{Z}^+$, where $f^n(\mu)$ is the n -th order derivative of the function $f(x)$. The Caputo fractional derivative is often used when the initial conditions are specified as conventional (integer order) derivatives.

The Gamma function, denoted by $\Gamma(z)$, is a generalization of the factorial operator and is used to define the fractional derivative in fractional calculus. The Gamma function is defined as [25]:

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^\infty x^{(z-1)} e^{-x} dt. \quad (5)$$

The Gamma function is defined for non-negative integers as $\Gamma(n) = (n-1)!$, and for other nonnegative values of z it can be computed by Abramowitz and Stegun [25]:

$$\Gamma(z) = \frac{e^{-\gamma z}}{z} \prod_{k=1}^\infty \left(\left(1 + \frac{z}{k}\right)^{-1} e^{\frac{z}{k}} \right), \quad (6)$$

where γ is the Euler–Mascheroni constant ($\gamma = 0.57721\dots$).

¹ https://gitlab.com/irafm-ai/frac_calc_ann

The fractional derivative, represented above, can be modified by replacing the factorial with the Gamma function. The definition provided in the following statement represents the fractional derivative of the function $f(x) = x^k$ for $k, x \geq 0$:

$$D^a x^k = \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(k+1-a)} x^{k-a}. \quad (7)$$

The Gamma function allows for the definition of the fractional derivative for non-integer values of k , while the factorial is only defined for integers. This allows for a more general and flexible formulation of the fractional derivative.

In machine learning, fractional derivatives and integrals have been used in various ways. For example, they have been used to design activation functions, as discussed in [4]. They can also be used in the design of loss functions, where they can capture more complex patterns in the data.

3. Exploring fractional variants of activation functions

Activation functions can be categorized into families utilizing fractional calculus. By representing the fractional derivative of an activation function, other activation functions within the same family can be mathematically derived.

3.1. Fractional GELU (FGELU)

GELU activation function is commonly used in transformers [26]. It was introduced in [27].

$$f(x) = 0.5x \left(1 + \tanh \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} (x + 0.044715x^3) \right) \right).$$

Fractional GELU is defined using the Grünwald–Letnikov fractional derivative:

$$D^a f(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2h^a} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(a+1)(x-nh)}{\Gamma(n+1)\Gamma(1-n+a)} \cdot (1 + \tanh \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} ((x-nh) + 0.044715(x-nh)^3) \right)). \quad (8)$$

3.2. Fractional Mish (FMish)

Mish activation function (used, for example, in the detection algorithm YOLOv4 [28]) is defined as:

$$f(x) = x \cdot \tanh(\ln(1 + e^x)) = x \cdot \frac{(e^x + 1)^2 - 1}{(e^x + 1)^2 + 1}.$$

Fractional Mish is computed as:

$$D^a f(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{h^a} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(a+1)(x-nh)}{\Gamma(n+1)\Gamma(1-n+a)} \cdot \frac{(e^{x-nh} + 1)^2 - 1}{(e^{x-nh} + 1)^2 + 1}. \quad (9)$$

3.3. Fractional Sigmoid (FSig)

The Sigmoid is one of the well-established functions in statistics and machine learning. It is commonly used as an activation function in the last layer (to squeeze output into $[0, 1]$) but not inside the networks. The function is defined as:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}.$$

The fractional Sigmoid can be implemented using the soft plus function or by directly applying the fractional derivative to the Sigmoid function:

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{h^a} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\Gamma(a+1)}{\Gamma(n+1)\Gamma(1-n+a)(1 + e^{-x+nh})} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 2. FALU and its fractional derivatives with fixed $\beta = 1$. The left graph shows FALU with our fix, notice smooth transition between the 0.9 and 1.1 derivative. The graph on the right shows derivatives with the original FALU formulation. Notice how 1.1 derivative is approximately 2 derivative.

Fig. 3. Fractional sigmoid with matched and mismatched N h pair. Left: $N = 2$ and $h = 0.5$. Right: $N = 3$ and $h = 0.5$.

3.4. Fractional adaptive linear unit (FALU)

The FALU was introduced in [5] as a flexible family of functions parameterized by two variables, α and β . Here $\alpha = a$ for the sake of consistency. The authors emphasize the ease of implementing this activation function in neural networks as the formula consists of simple arithmetic operations and the Sigmoid function, completely avoiding the gamma function. Although the approximation for $a \in [0, 1]$ is accurate, the approximation for $a \in (1, 2]$ is inaccurate; see Fig. 2. We propose a simple change: $a \rightarrow (a - 1)$ (bold part of the formula). FALU limits $a \in [0, 2]$ and $\beta \in [1, 10]$ and is defined as:

$$\approx \begin{cases} g(x, \beta) + a\sigma(\beta x)(1 - g(x, \beta)), & a \in [0, 1], \\ h(x, \beta) + (a - 1)\sigma(\beta x)(1 - 2h(x, \beta)), & a \in (1, 2]. \end{cases}$$

Here, $h(x, \beta)$ is defined as $g(x, \beta) + \sigma(x)(1 - g(x, \beta))$ and $g(x, 1) = g(x) = x\sigma(x)$.

4. Fractional hyperparameter tuning

All fractional activation functions share two variables that make implementation rather difficult. The first is the variable h in $\frac{1}{h^a}$ and the second is the upper bound of the summation ∞ in $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty}$. We will refer to the upper bound of summation as N . Eq. (1), shows that both values are intertwined.

As N increases, so does the precision of the fractional derivative approximation, similar to the Taylor series. Examining the term $f(x - nh)$ in Eq. (1), we can see that the fractional derivative at point x uses the interval $[x - Nh, x]$ for computation. To keep this interval constant for different N , we adjust h :

$$h = \frac{1}{\max(1, N - 1)}. \quad (11)$$

Fig. 3 illustrates the case where h is set correctly and incorrectly.

To find a suitable N value, we perform training runs with varying N . The runs have identical training settings as described in Section 5, except the training dataset size and number of epochs. We train ResNet-20 on 50% of CIFAR-10 for 100 epochs and EfficientNet-B0 on 10% of IN-1K for 30 epochs.

Weight decay that we use in our experiments has a unwanted effect on the fractional order of the activation functions. It pushes the fractional orders towards zero, as the fractional orders are included in the model parameters. We prevent fractional orders decaying by setting their decay factor to $\gamma = 0$.

Fig. 4. Test accuracies of the fractional sigmoid, Mish, and GELU in a first, second, and third row respectively. The results in the left column are obtained by training ResNet-20 on 50% of the CIFAR-10 training set. The results in the right column are obtained by training EfficientNet-B0 on 10% of IN-1K training set.

Table 1

Increase/decrease in time and memory complexity of fractional activation functions compared to their non-fractional counterparts. All fractional activation functions have $N = 1$ in the comparison.

Net/Data	FSig	FMish	FGELU
<i>Time</i>			
ResNet20 CIFAR-10	1.84x	1.78x	1.84x
EfficientNetB0 IN-1K	2.41x	3.42x	2.28x
<i>Memory</i>			
ResNet20 CIFAR-10	1.23x	1.35x	1.23x
EfficientNetB0 IN-1K	1.82x	2.71x	1.65x

Fig. 4 shows \times increase/decrease in memory and time complexity and test accuracy. The missing result in the second row (FMish) is caused by the training falling into NaN. We tried to stabilize training with gradient clipping; however, the clipping norm would have to be very small and would hinder the results of other activation functions.

In almost all runs, both the memory and the time complexity increase approximately linearly, although the time complexity increases faster (see Table 1).

We used the **highest accuracy** N for full-train experiments in Section 5. We use IN-1K as a proxy for datasets with similar resolution (CalTech-256 [29] and Food-101 [30]) to select N .

5. Activation function performance

We evaluate the performance of Sigmoid, Mish, and GELU and their fractional counterparts, as well as ReLU, PReLU, and FALU. We chose ReLU because it is widely used, PReLU because it includes trainable parameters, and FALU because of its promising results. All of the following results are seeded, reproducible, and use deterministic algorithms. Please refer to our repository.

5.1. ResNets and CIFAR-10

We train several ResNet variants designed for the CIFAR-10 dataset. CIFAR-10 characteristics are the small resolution of 32×32 pixels and the low number of classes (10).

Experiments setting: We train for 200 epochs with a 5-epoch warm-up. We use SGD with 0.9 momentum, $5e-4$ weight decay, and an learning rate of 0.1 that decreases at 30%, 60%, and 80% of total training steps. Data are fed to the network in batches of 128 images augmented with padded random cropping, horizontal flipping,

Table 2

CIFAR-10 test accuracies of different ResNet/activation function combinations. FGELU, FSig and FMish N is set to 1, 2 and 2 respectively.

ResNet	20	32	44	56	110
#params	0.27 M	0.46 M	0.66 M	0.85 M	1.70 M
ReLU	92.52	93.21	93.78	93.85	94.41
PReLU	92.85	93.41	94.12	94.17	94.67
FALU	92.21	93.47	92.83	93.22	92.05
GELU	92.95	93.47	93.08	93.12	92.99
FGELU	93.14 (\uparrow)	93.39(\downarrow)	93.22(\uparrow)	93.54(\uparrow)	92.83(\downarrow)
Sig	83.56	78.27	75.56	79.58	15.42
FSig	91.78(\uparrow)	88.98(\uparrow)	86.99(\uparrow)	86.49(\uparrow)	17.00(\uparrow)
Mish	92.57	92.67	92.67	92.51	92.37
FMish	91.75(\downarrow)	92.98(\uparrow)	92.19(\downarrow)	91.39(\downarrow)	91.27(\downarrow)

and normalization. Furthermore, we use label smoothing 0.1, gradient clipping by max norm 10, and FP16 precision. We track and report the best overall test accuracy. The fractional activation functions have N and h set according to Section 4 results.

Table 2 displays the best test accuracies for various ResNet and activation functions on CIFAR-10.

FSig accuracies show better performance across all ResNets. We believe that while the sigmoid is not suitable for being an activation function inside networks, changing its shape through fractional calculus helps mitigate some undesirable properties. FGELU outperformed GELU in 3 runs. Interestingly, FGELU $N = 1$ is identical to GELU and yet it produced a different result. We attribute this fact to the difference in the calculation. FMish performed the worst out of our 3 fractional activation functions, being as much as 1.12% behind in accuracy. FALU² did not outperform ReLU, PReLU, and GELU in general. Our FALU experimental results differ from the published results. The main difference between published results and ours is the higher accuracy of the baseline, non-fractional activation functions.

Fig. 5 histograms illustrate the FOD distribution at the beginning and end of the training process across experiments from Table 2. The fractional order tends to converge towards 0 and 2 in all experiments. FMish fractional order progressively moves to 0 as the ResNet depth increases. FGELU is not present in the figure because its fractional order does not affect Eq. (8) when $N = 1$. Intuitively, fractional activation functions should have an edge over the non-fractional counterparts. However, based on our experiments, this is a case only for sigmoid. Table 2 shows that only two activation functions lead to a consistent increase in performance: ReLU and PReLU, which are the original ResNet paper activation function and its variation.

We hypothesize that fractional activation functions negatively change the surface of the error function. This is likely due to the complexity of the computation, especially the gamma function. Our thesis is supported by the comparison of train and test loss in Fig. 6. While train losses of both fractional and non-fractional activations converge similarly (except for FSig), the test losses do not. Given that the experiments are seeded and deterministic, each model was presented with the same sequence of batches.

The test loss is computed using test data that lie in proximity to the train data. The significant difference between train and test losses indicates narrow local minima on the loss surface, where any sample-wise divergence leads to a spike in loss, indicating a non-convex surface. This concept is visualized in Fig. 1 [31] that shows how skip connections change the loss surface of ResNets. The fractional activation functions change the ResNet architecture and loss surface. It becomes challenging to find good local minima where the model generalizes well.

² In all experiments, we initialized and kept $a \in [0, 2]$ and $\beta \in [1, 10]$.

Table 3
Test accuracies of different model/dataset/activation function combinations described in Section 5.2.

Dataset	ReLU	PReLU	SILU	FALU	GELU	FGELU N = 1	Sig	FSig N = 2	Mish	FMish N = 2
<i>EfficientNetB0</i> [32]										
IN-1K	66.66	73.41	69.09	67.62	70.78	70.99(†)	28.5	60.18(†)	54.82*	53.69*(↓)
CalTech-256	62.86	60.12	61.39	59.32	62.62	63.13(†)	47.74	63.17 (†)	60.97	58.53(↓)
Food-101	85.82	84.10	85.12	83.72	85.82	85.77(↓)	55.69	83.82(†)	85.35	00.00(↓)
<i>MobileNetV4-small</i> [33]										
CalTech-256	51.87	44.42	52.74	49.73	52.63	53.58(†)	12.86	53.66 (†)	52.06	51.99(↓)
Food-101	78.00	72.52	76.6	77.37	78.21	78.79(†)	30.36	78.90 (†)	76.36	77.70(†)
<i>MobileNetV4-medium</i> [33]										
CalTech-256	57.18	52.27	55.73	00.00	56.94	56.68(↓)	08.09	56.73(†)	55.23	00.00(↓)
Food-101	80.9	76.88	76.65	82.19	79.71	79.81(†)	22.09	77.51(†)	77.28	78.03(†)
<i>ConvNextV2-atto</i> [34]										
CalTech-256	49.44	50.46	47.2	47.39	45.53	46.45(†)	26.55	33.23(†)	47.24	47.86(†)
Food-101	77.33	76.86	70.69	69.03	75.45	74.90(↓)	29.49	42.44(†)	72.97	73.31(†)
<i>ConvNextV2-femto</i> [34]										
CalTech-256	50.40	50.69	47.14	45.09	47.73	47.59(↓)	24.65	37.55(†)	47.64	48.30(†)
Food-101	79.10	76.04	73.37	70.19	75.75	74.77(↓)	31.35	48.51(†)	70.74	72.24(†)
<i>EVA-02-tiny</i> [35]										
CalTech-256	36.77	37.39	36.72	36.24	36.9	36.64(↓)	36.57	35.12(↓)	36.40	36.58(†)
Food-101	70.38	70.41	71.08	69.08	70.01	70.46(†)	63.52	66.48(†)	71.03	68.99(↓)

Fig. 5. Distribution of FOD at the beginning and the end of the training.

Fig. 6. Train (left) and test (right) loss over the training of ResNet-20 on CIFAR-10.

5.2. Additional architectures and datasets

We train several models using three datasets: IN-1K, CalTech-256, and Food-101. These datasets have in common a higher number of

classes, up to 1000, and higher (variable) image resolution. In the case of CalTech-256, we use the train-test split procedure from [36], selecting 60 train images per class.

Base experiments setting: We train for 60 epochs with a 2-epoch warm-up. We use SGD with 0.9 momentum, 1e-4 weight decay, and an initial learning rate of 2.5e-2 with a cosine annealing warm restarts scheduler ($T_0 = 4$, $mult = 2$). Data are fed to the network in batches of 64 images augmented with random resized cropping, horizontal flipping, color jitter, and normalization. Training images have a resolution of 224×224 , and testing images have a resolution of 320×320 [37]. Furthermore, we use label smoothing 0.1, gradient clipping by max norm 10, and FP16 precision, identical to Section 5.1. We track and report the best overall test accuracy. The fractional activation functions have N and h set according to Section 4.

CalTech-256 and Food-101: We change the number of epochs for CalTech-256 to 256 and Food-101 to 90.

EVA-02-Tiny: Eva-02 is transformer and therefore we change optimizer to AdamW with default parameters and learning rate 1e-4. We maintain the same resolution for both training and testing (224×224) to ensure compatibility with the transformer input patch format.

Table 3 shows similar results to Table 2. **FSig** consistently outperforms Sig. It achieves the best or close to the best accuracies, except for EVA-02-tiny. **FGELU** does not deviate from the GELU too much and in general has inconsistent behavior. **FMish** is similar performance-wise to GELU; however, it has instability issues that leads to NaN crashing. In order to run full training, we used stricter gradient clipping with a maximum norm of 1 (* results in Table 3). The stricter gradient clipping also led to fewer oscillations and spikes in test loss (Fig. 7). In certain cases, even strict gradient clipping did not help to avoid NaN crashing. Those are the 00.00 results in Table 3.

Overall, the fractional activation functions tend to outperform non-fractional but do not reach the highest accuracies among other activation functions. Training and testing losses generally follow the same pattern as the losses in Section 5.1. The spikes in training and testing losses are caused by restarts of the learning rate.

6. Conclusion and future work

Fractional activation functions present a flexible and expressive alternative to traditional activation functions by incorporating a fractional order derivative as a tunable parameter. This paper introduced the FGELU and FMish functions and demonstrated through experiments that fractional activation functions, particularly the fractional

Fig. 7. Train (left) and test (right) loss evolution over the training of EfficientNet-B0.

Sigmoid, can outperform standard ones in some cases. However, their performance remains inconsistent across all scenarios.

An important challenge identified is the computational complexity of fractional activation functions, which scales unfavorably with increasing parameter N . Future work should focus on optimizing this scaling and exploring strategies to dynamically select optimal N values to balance memory, computational time, and accuracy. Additionally, further research should investigate alternative fractional derivatives, such as Caputo or Riemann–Liouville, to enhance efficiency and accuracy in neural networks. Continued exploration of these methods and automated parameter tuning is essential for advancing the practical applicability of fractional activation functions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vojtech Molek: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zahra Alijani:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The study described is from the project Research of Excellence on Digital Technologies and Wellbeing CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004583 which is co-financed by the European Union.

This article has been produced with the financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH – Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition.

Data availability

All code and experimental details are publicly available at https://gitlab.com/irafm-ai/frac_calc_ann.

References

- [1] M.D. Ortigueira, F. Coito, From differences to derivatives, *Fract. Calc. Appl. Anal.* 7 (4) (2004) 459.
- [2] C.Z. Aguilar, J. Gómez-Aguilar, V. Alvarado-Martínez, H. Romero-Ugalde, Fractional order neural networks for system identification, *Chaos Solitons Fractals* 130 (2020) 109444.
- [3] A. Wu, L. Liu, T. Huang, Z. Zeng, Mittag-Leffler stability of fractional-order neural networks in the presence of generalized piecewise constant arguments, *Neural Netw.* 85 (2017) 118–127.
- [4] J. Zamora Esquivel, A. Cruz Vargas, R. Camacho Perez, P. Lopez Meyer, H. Cordouier, O. Tickoo, Adaptive activation functions using fractional calculus, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops*, 2019.
- [5] J. Zamora, A.D. Rhodes, L. Nachman, Fractional adaptive linear units, in: *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 36, 2022, pp. 8988–8996.
- [6] M.A. Kassem, A.A. Abohany, A.A.A. El-Mageed, K.M. Hosny, A novel deep learning model for detection of inconsistency in e-commerce websites, *Neural Comput. Appl.* 36 (17) (2024) 10339–10353.
- [7] P.N. Ahmad, Y. Liu, I. Ullah, M. Shabaz, Enhancing coherence and diversity in multi-class slogan generation systems, *ACM Trans. Asian Low-Resour. Lang. Inf. Process.* 23 (8) (2024) 1–24.
- [8] D. Boomhead, D. Lowe, Radial basis functions, multi-variable functional interpolation, and adaptive networks, *R. Signals Radar Establ.* (1988).
- [9] K. Fukushima, Visual feature extraction by a multilayered network of analog threshold elements, *IEEE Trans. Syst. Sci. Cybern.* 5 (4) (1969) 322–333.
- [10] C. Dugas, Y. Bengio, F. Bélisle, C. Nadeau, R. Garcia, Incorporating second-order functional knowledge for better option pricing, *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 13 (2000).
- [11] P. Ramachandran, B. Zoph, Q.V. Le, Searching for activation functions, 2017, arXiv preprint arXiv:1710.05941.
- [12] D. Misra, Mish: A self regularized non-monotonic activation function, 2019, arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.08681.
- [13] T. Elsken, J.H. Metzen, F. Hutter, Neural architecture search: A survey, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 20 (1) (2019) 1997–2017.
- [14] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Delving deep into rectifiers: Surpassing human-level performance on imagenet classification, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2015, pp. 1026–1034.
- [15] A. Ivanov, Fractional activation functions in feedforward artificial neural networks, in: *2018 20th International Symposium on Electrical Apparatus and Technologies, SIELA, IEEE*, 2018, pp. 1–4.
- [16] A. Krizhevsky, G. Hinton, et al., Learning Multiple Layers of Features from Tiny Images, Toronto, ON, Canada, 2009.
- [17] O. Russakovsky, J. Deng, H. Su, J. Krause, S. Satheesh, S. Ma, Z. Huang, A. Karpathy, A. Khosla, M. Bernstein, A.C. Berg, L. Fei-Fei, ImageNet large scale visual recognition challenge, *Int. J. Comput. Vis. (IJCV)* 115 (3) (2015) 211–252, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11263-015-0816-y>.
- [18] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Deep residual learning for image recognition, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [19] M.S. Job, P.H. Bhatija, M. Gupta, K. Bingi, B.R. Prusty, et al., Fractional rectified linear unit activation function and its variants, *Math. Probl. Eng.* 2022 (2022).
- [20] M. Kumar, U. Mehta, G. Cirrincione, Enhancing neural network classification using fractional-order activation functions, *AI Open* 5 (2024) 10–22.
- [21] R.A. Fisher, Iris, 1988, <http://dx.doi.org/10.24432/C56C76>, UCI Machine Learning Repository.
- [22] L. Deng, The mnist database of handwritten digit images for machine learning research, *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* 29 (6) (2012) 141–142.
- [23] H. Xiao, K. Rasul, R. Vollgraf, Fashion-mnist: a novel image dataset for benchmarking machine learning algorithms, 2017, arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.07747.
- [24] R. Herrmann, *Fractional Calculus-An Introduction for Physicists*, World Scientific Publishing, Singapore, 2011.
- [25] M. Abramowitz, I.A. Stegun, Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables, tenth ed., in: National Bureau of Standards Applied Mathematics Series 55. Tenth Printing, ERIC, 1972, pp. 253–266.
- [26] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A.N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, I. Polosukhin, Attention is all you need, *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 30 (2017).
- [27] D. Hendrycks, K. Gimpel, Gaussian error linear units (gelus), 2016, arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.08415.
- [28] A. Bochkovskiy, C.-Y. Wang, H.-Y.M. Liao, Yolov4: Optimal speed and accuracy of object detection, 2020, arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.10934.
- [29] G. Griffin, A. Holub, P. Perona, et al., Caltech-256 Object Category Dataset, Technical Report 7694, California Institute of Technology Pasadena, 2007.
- [30] L. Bossard, M. Guillaumin, L. Van Gool, Food-101 – mining discriminative components with random forests, in: *European Conference on Computer Vision*, 2014.
- [31] H. Li, Z. Xu, G. Taylor, C. Studer, T. Goldstein, Visualizing the loss landscape of neural nets, *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 31 (2018).

- [32] M. Tan, Q. Le, Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks, in: International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR, 2019, pp. 6105–6114.
- [33] D. Qin, C. Leichner, M. Delakis, M. Forni, S. Luo, F. Yang, W. Wang, C. Banbury, C. Ye, B. Akin, et al., MobileNetV4: Universal models for the mobile ecosystem, in: European Conference on Computer Vision, Springer, 2025, pp. 78–96.
- [34] S. Woo, S. Debnath, R. Hu, X. Chen, Z. Liu, I.S. Kweon, S. Xie, Convnext v2: Co-designing and scaling convnets with masked autoencoders, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2023, pp. 16133–16142.
- [35] Y. Fang, Q. Sun, X. Wang, T. Huang, X. Wang, Y. Cao, Eva-02: A visual representation for neon genesis, *Image Vis. Comput.* 149 (2024) 105171.
- [36] W. Ge, X. Lin, Y. Yu, Weakly supervised complementary parts models for fine-grained image classification from the bottom up, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2019, pp. 3034–3043.
- [37] H. Touvron, A. Vedaldi, M. Douze, H. Jégou, Fixing the train-test resolution discrepancy, *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.* 32 (2019).